

EXPLORING THE BEHAVIOUR OF SUSTAINABLE CONCRETE WITH PORCELAIN TILE WASTE AND CALCIUM CARBONATE

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ABSTRACT

This project investigates the mechanical and durability performance of sustainable self-compacting concrete (SCC) incorporating recycled porcelain tile waste as a partial replacement for coarse aggregates, along with the addition of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) as a filler. Ceramic tiles are often dumped as waste material after it becomes useless. But it can be recycled and can be used as a construction material in present world which is seeking for alternative construction materials which are economical, environment friendly as well as provides same quality as that of a normal aggregate made of stones. Calcium carbonate is known to influence the setting time, strength, and durability of concrete. When used in concrete, CaCO_3 particles fill the voids between the cement particles, potentially enhancing the packing density and contributing to strength gain and durability. Its presence may also lead to a denser microstructure, improving resistance to cracking and other durability issues. The study aims to reduce environmental impact while maintaining or improving the structural quality of concrete. A detailed literature review identified key knowledge gaps and guided the formulation of objectives. Preliminary material characterization tests were conducted to determine the suitability of waste materials for concrete production. The percentage of ceramic tiles in the concrete mix is varied from 0%,10%,25% and 50% and also the addition of varying percentages ie 10%,20% and 30% of calcium carbonate to get more strength. Various mix proportions were developed and optimized through mechanical strength tests and durability assessments. Furthermore, a finite element analysis of a fixed beam was carried out using ANSYS Workbench (version 2023 R1) with SOLID185 elements to simulate the structural behavior of the developed concrete mixes under different loading conditions. The results demonstrate the potential of incorporating industrial waste materials into concrete to achieve sustainability without compromising performance.

Key words: Porcelain tile waste, Calcium Carbonate (CaCO_3), Mechanical properties, ANSYS Workbench

INTRODUCTION

The sustainable development of construction materials has led to a focus on eco-friendly concrete mixtures that incorporate industrial waste. Porcelain tile waste is one such material, often discarded in landfills that could potentially serve as a replacement for traditional aggregates in concrete. This study explores the structural behavior and performance of sustainable concrete with porcelain tile waste, using finite element analysis (FEA) in ANSYS to model and predict its behavior under various loading conditions. The insights gained from ANSYS simulations are essential for understanding the feasibility of using porcelain waste in structural applications, ensuring it meets performance and durability standards.

As part of efforts to make efficient use of industrial wastes available materials, this study was carried out to investigate the influences of replacement of conventional coarse aggregates by ceramic tiles on the mechanical properties of concrete as well as to assess the effect of moisture content on it.

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) using software like ANSYS provides valuable insights into the behavior of complex structures under various loading conditions. By simulating concrete behavior in ANSYS, researchers can predict responses to compressive, tensile, and flexural stresses, which are critical for determining its suitability in structural applications. FEA also aids in optimizing mix designs by visualizing the internal stress distribution and failure mechanisms, particularly beneficial when incorporating non-traditional materials like porcelain waste.

Using porcelain waste in concrete aligns with sustainable building practices, reducing reliance on virgin aggregates and minimizing landfill waste. The environmental benefits include lower carbon emissions, conservation of natural resources, and efficient waste recycling. Economically, adopting porcelain waste can reduce material costs, especially in regions where porcelain waste is abundant. However, additional processing for waste materials and optimal replacement levels are necessary to maintain concrete quality without incurring excess costs.

OBJECTIVES

To optimize the mix proportions of porcelain tile waste and calcium carbonate for use in self-compacting concrete.

To achieve high mechanical performance (strength) and enhanced durability with recycled and sustainable materials.

To minimize the environmental impact by incorporating recycled materials and reducing the carbon footprint.

To use ANSYS simulations to predict and optimize the concrete mix design before physical testing, leading to a more efficient and cost-effective process.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the project, as illustrated in Figure 3.1, outlines the systematic approach adopted to investigate the behavior of sustainable concrete incorporating varying percentages of porcelain tile waste and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3). A comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify existing research gaps, which informed the formulation of the project objectives. Initially, preliminary tests were carried out to determine the physical and chemical properties of the constituent materials required for the concrete mix design. Subsequently, several concrete mixes were prepared by replacing coarse aggregates with different percentages of porcelain tile waste and incorporating CaCO_3 . These mixes were then evaluated through mechanical strength tests and durability assessments to determine the optimal combination. Additionally, this chapter details the finite element modeling and structural analysis performed using ANSYS Workbench, providing deeper insight into the behavior of the sustainable concrete under various loading conditions.

Cement

Portland Pozzolana Cement (PPC) is a blended cement made by intergrinding Portland cement clinker, pozzolanic material (fly ash, silica fumes, volcanic ash, or calcined clay), and a small amount of gypsum. It is widely used in construction due to its enhanced durability and environmental benefits. PPC doesn't typically have a 53-grade equivalent as its focus is on durability, long-term strength, and sustainability. If higher strength is required, a mix design optimization or blending with OPC might be considered. As per IS 1489, properties of PPC can be obtained.

Property	Value
Specific gravity	3.14
Fineness modulus	2%
Initial setting time	33 min.
Final setting time	360 min.
consistency	31.25%

Material Properties of Cement Used

Fine aggregate

Aggregate which passed through 4.75 mm IS Sieve and retained on 75micron (0.075mm) IS Sieve is termed as fine aggregate. Fine aggregate is added to concrete to assist workability and to bring uniformity in mixture. Usually, the natural river sand is used as fine aggregate. Washed M sand conforming to Indian standards is used in this project. IS code for fine aggregate is IS 2386.

Property	Value
Fineness modulus	2.624
Specific gravity	2.62
Moisture content (%)	2.4
Water absorption (%)	2

Material properties of fine aggregate used

Coarse aggregate

The coarse aggregate for the works should be river gravel or crushed stone. Angular shape aggregate of size is 20mm and below. The aggregate which passes through 75mm sieve and retain on 4.75mm are known as coarse aggregate.

It should be hard, strong, dense, durable, clean, and free from clay or loamy admixtures or quarry refuse or vegetable matter. The pieces of aggregates should be cubical, or rounded shaped and should have granular or crystalline or smooth (but not glossy) non-powdery surfaces. Aggregates should be properly screened and if necessary washed clean before use. Coarse aggregates containing flat, elongated or flaky pieces or mica should be rejected. The grading of coarse aggregates should be as per specifications of IS 383-1970.

In this project, maximum normal size of coarse aggregate is 20mm for controlled concrete. Machine crushed granite obtained from a Local Quarry was used as coarse aggregate.

Property	Value
Fineness modulus	3.61
Specific gravity	2.8
Moisture content (%)	0.23
Water absorption(%)	0.5

Material Properties Of Coarse Aggregate Used

Water

The water should be fit for mixing. The water should not have high concentrations of sodium and potassium and there is a danger of alkali-aggregate reaction. Natural waters that are slightly acidic are harmless, but water containing humic or other organic acids may adversely affect the hardening of concrete. Such water as well as highly alkaline water should be tested. The water should conform to IS 456-2000 standards. Generally, water satisfactory for mixing is also suitable for curing purposes. However, it is essential that curing water should be free from substances that attack hardened concrete like free CO₂ etc.

Ceramic tiles

The ceramic wastes are obtained from a local building that has been demolished. The waste ceramics are crushed into pieces with hammer beats. The ceramic tiles which are of 20 mm size can be used in varying proportion as a partial replacement of the coarse aggregate. These ceramic tiles are added to the concrete in different percentage of the total coarse aggregate such as 0%, 20%, 30% and 40%.

Property	Value
Fineness modulus	3.65
Specific gravity	2.5
Water absorption (%)	0.7

Material Properties Of Ceramic tile Used

Calcium carbonate

Calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) is increasingly used as a partial cement replacement in concrete to promote sustainability and reduce CO₂ emissions. Although it is not a pozzolanic material, it acts effectively as a micro-filler and nucleation site, enhancing particle packing, workability, and early hydration. When used in optimized proportions (typically 10–30%), calcium carbonate can improve early-age strength and durability by refining the microstructure and accelerating cement hydration. Its benefits are especially notable when combined with supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs), as it enhances the overall performance and rheology of the mix. However, excessive replacement may reduce long-term strength, so careful mix design and particle fineness are essential. Overall, calcium carbonate is a promising additive for producing green, high-performance concrete with improved fresh and hardened properties.

The specific gravity of calcium carbonate is typically around **2.7–2.9**, depending on its purity and crystalline form. Specific gravity is the ratio of the material's density to the density of water at a standard temperature (usually 4°C).

particle size distribution curve

Table below shows various mix designations with detailed description which are used for this project.

MIX DESIGNATION	DESCRIPTION
M1	Conventional concrete
M2	Concrete mix with 10% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tiles in SSD condition
M3	Concrete mix with 25% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tiles in SSD condition
M4	Concrete mix with 50% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tiles in SSD condition
M5	Concrete mix with 25% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tile and addition of 10% CaCO ₃
M6	Concrete mix with 25% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tile and addition of 20% CaCO ₃
M7	Concrete mix with 25% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tile and addition of 30% CaCO ₃

mix designations

Experimental test results and discussions

Based on the mix design obtained specimens were casted to find out the strength of the concrete. Cubes of size 150×150×150 are casted to find out the compressive strength and cylinders with 150 mm diameter and 300 mm height are casted for determining the split tensile strength and prisms of size 500×100×100mm are casted for finding out the split tensile strength. Specimens made with the obtained mix proportions are the control specimens .cubes, cylinders and beams are also prepared for 0%,10,25% and 50% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tiles and addition of calcium carbonate in varying proportions.(ie , 10,20 and 30%)

Mix preparation

Mix	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	Split tensile strength (N/mm ²)	Flexural strength (N/mm ²)
M ₁	27.5	3.25	3.75
M ₂	24.6	2.57	3.5
M ₃	27.77	3.28	3.9
M ₄	22.3	2.37	3.25
M ₅	29.2	3.4	4.05
M ₆	27.75	3.06	3.8
M ₇	29	3.3	3.82

28th day strength test results

Compressive strength test result

The graph given below shows the variation of compressive strength with the replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tiles. The different mixes used such as the conventional concrete mix and mixes with 10%,25% and 50% replacement are shown on the X- axis and the compressive strengths in N/mm^2 is shown in the Y-axis.

Compressive strength for replacement with ceramic tile at 28th day

On analyzing the graph it can be seen that the compressive strength is maximum for 25% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tile. The compressive strength of concrete with 25% replacement by ceramic tile shows a slight increase than the conventional concrete ie, 0.72% increase for the 28th day.

7.3.1.2 Split tensile strength test results

The graph given below shows the variation of split tensile strength with the replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tiles. The different mixes used such as the conventional concrete mix and mixes with 10%, 25% and 50% replacement are shown on the X- axis and the split tensile strengths in N/mm^2 is shown in the Y-axis.

On analysing the graph it can be seen that the split tensile strength is maximum for 25% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tile. The split tensile strength of concrete with 25% replacement by ceramic tile shows a slight increase than the conventional concrete ie, 0.92% increase for the 28th day

split tensile strength for replacement with ceramic tile at 28th day

split tensile strength test specimen after testing

Flexural strength test result

The graph given below shows the variation of flexural strength with the replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tiles. The different mixes used such as the conventional concrete mix and mixes with 10%,25% and 50% replacement are shown on the X- axis and the flexural strengths in N/mm^2 is shown in the Y-axis.

Fig 7.4 flexural strength for replacement with ceramic tile at 28th day

On analyzing the graph it can be seen that the flexural strength is maximum for 25% replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tile. The flexural strength of concrete with 25% replacement by ceramic tile shows a slight increase than the conventional concrete ie, 0.96% increase for the 28th day.

Modulus of elasticity test results

The graph given below shows the variation of stress-strain with the replacement of coarse aggregate by ceramic tiles. The different mixes used such as the conventional concrete mix and mixes with 10%,25% and 50% replacement. Strain values are shown on the X- axis and stress values in N/mm^2 are shown in the Y-axis.

Stress- Strain curve for different concrete mixes

Specimen	Modulus of elasticity (MPa)
Conventional Concrete	24,285.71
10% Ceramic Tile	22,171.43
25% Ceramic Tile	26,257.14
50% Ceramic Tile	20,542.86

Modulus of elasticity test result

In ANSYS Workbench, the beam modeling process begins by creating a new Static Structural analysis system and defining the geometry using DesignModeler or SpaceClaim. A beam can be modeled as a line body, and a suitable cross-section (e.g., rectangular, circular) is assigned using the "Cross Section" and "Cross Section Assignment" features. After defining the geometry, appropriate material properties—such as Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, and density—are assigned in the Engineering Data workspace, typically using Structural Steel or a custom-defined material. The model is then opened in ANSYS Mechanical, where meshing is applied to the beam by refining the number of divisions along the line body to ensure accurate results. Boundary conditions are defined by applying supports at the ends of the beam, such as fixed or simply supported, depending on the desired setup. Loading conditions, such as point loads or distributed forces, are then applied to the beam to simulate real-world scenarios. After solving the model, the results are reviewed using deformation plots, stress

distributions, and internal force diagrams such as bending moment and shear force diagrams, which provide insight into the structural performance of the beam under the applied loads.

Material model

Model of beam meshing

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS in Ansys

Equivalent elastic strain analysis result

The above figure shows equivalent elastic strain of beam subjected to gradual loading at a simulation time of 1s. Maximum Equivalent Elastic Strain obtained is 0.00348467 mm/mm (in red zones). Minimum Equivalent Elastic Strain obtained is 5.7629×10^{-6} mm/mm (in dark blue zones). The Red indicates areas of highest strain, and blue indicates areas of lowest strain. The highest strains occur near the middle and at some vertical elements, indicating localized deformation. Strain distribution is more intense along the upper and lower curved members, suggesting bending effects are significant.

Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress analysis result

The above figure shows Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress of beam subjected to gradual loading at a simulation time of 1s. The analysis result of Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress are as follows. Maximum Stress: 5.1489×10^7 Pa (≈ 51.49 MPa) – shown in red. Minimum Stress: 1.3096×10^6 Pa (≈ 1.31 MPa) – shown in dark blue. Red/Orange areas: High stress concentrations, likely critical zones for failure analysis or reinforcement. Blue/Green areas: Low stress zones, indicating minimal load impact. The highest stress concentrations are located at the central region and connections between horizontal and vertical members. This pattern is typical in bending structures, where mid-span and joint areas often carry the most loads. The von-Mises stress distribution helps determine whether yielding might occur under the applied load.

Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress of beam analysis result

The above figure shows Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress of beam subjected to gradual loading at a simulation time of 1s. Maximum Deformation: 0.027336 mm (at red-colored areas). Minimum Deformation: 0 mm (dark blue zones). Red: Regions of maximum displacement. Purple/Blue: Regions of minimal or zero displacement. Maximum deformation occurs in the central region, suggesting that the structure is experiencing bending or flexural deformation. The deformation is relatively small ($<$

0.03 mm), indicating the structure is stiff and possibly under modest loading. The symmetrical contour pattern implies a uniform loading or symmetrical boundary condition.

Total deformation of beam analysis result(25%PTA)

The screenshot shows a static structural analysis conducted in ANSYS 2023 R1, focusing on the total deformation of a structure under a specific loading condition. The analysis setup includes fixed support and applied force, with results displayed under the “Solution (A6)” branch. The “Total Deformation” result is highlighted, and the contour plot in the graphics window shows the deformation distribution across the body, ranging from 0 mm (minimum, in blue) to approximately 0.1159 mm (maximum, in red). The color gradient clearly indicates that the maximum deformation occurs near the center of the structure, likely at the point farthest from the fixed supports, which is consistent with typical bending behavior. The animation settings and deformation scale help visualize structural response over time, enhancing interpretation of the results.

Fig.8.15 Total deformation of reinforcement analysis result (25%PTA)

The screenshot shows a detailed deformation analysis in ANSYS 2023 R1 under a static structural environment, specifically visualizing “Total Deformation 2.” This result appears to represent the deformation distribution across multiple structural bodies (10 bodies, as noted in the "Details" pane), possibly in an assembly or reinforced structure. The wireframe display enhances clarity by revealing internal and external deformation patterns.

The deformation scale indicates a maximum displacement of 0.11494 mm and a minimum of 0 mm, consistent with boundary conditions likely involving fixed supports and applied forces. The color contour follows the standard rainbow scale, highlighting that the central or unsupported regions experience the most deformation (red zones), while areas near constraints show minimal movement (blue zones). This deformation pattern suggests a symmetric structural behavior under load.

Overall, the results confirm elastic behavior with small displacements, indicating that the structure remains within safe limits under the applied loading conditions.

Total equivalent stress - analysis result (25%PTA)

The ANSYS simulation results indicate that the structure experiences a maximum equivalent (von-Mises) stress of 476.63 MPa and a minimum of 1.4628 MPa, with stress concentration observed primarily near the boundary regions or areas of applied loads and constraints. The stress distribution shows that most of the structure is under lower stress levels, suggesting an overall balanced load distribution. The maximum total deformation is approximately 0.11494 mm, indicating limited displacement under the applied loading conditions. This deformation pattern is consistent with bending behavior, likely resulting from transverse loading on a fixed or supported structure. From a design perspective, the structural integrity appears satisfactory if the material's yield strength exceeds the observed maximum stress. However, if the yield strength is lower, areas of high stress may pose a risk

of failure and could require design modifications, such as changing the geometry, reinforcing critical zones, or selecting a more suitable material.

Total equivalent strain - analysis result (25%PTA)

The equivalent elastic strain results from the ANSYS simulation reveal a maximum strain value of 0.0032107 mm/mm and a minimum of 0.00010917 mm/mm. The strain distribution is relatively uniform across the majority of the structure, with localized regions of higher strain appearing near the corners and boundaries, likely where constraints or loads are applied. These higher strain zones indicate areas undergoing more significant deformation under stress, which can be critical for assessing material behavior and durability. Since strain directly relates to the material's deformation capacity, these results suggest that while the majority of the structure experiences moderate elastic strain, the regions with elevated values should be evaluated against material limits to ensure they remain within the elastic range and do not lead to permanent deformation or failure.

Fig.8.18 Load-deformation graph (25%PTA)

The Load-Deformation graph compares the mechanical behavior of various concrete mixes incorporating different percentages of Porcelain Tile Aggregate (PTA) — 10%, 25%, and 50% — against a conventional concrete mix. All samples exhibit a near-linear trend, indicating elastic behavior within the observed deformation range. Among the mixes, the 25% PTA sample demonstrates the highest load-bearing capacity, reaching a peak load of approximately 32,000 N at around 0.14 mm deformation. This suggests that the 25% PTA mix achieves an optimal balance between stiffness and strength. The conventional mix also performs well, slightly outperforming the 10% and 50% PTA mixes, which show lower load capacities. The 50% PTA mix shows the lowest stiffness, evidenced by its relatively flatter slope, indicating greater deformation under lower loads. Overall, the graph indicates that moderate replacement (especially at 25%) of natural aggregate with PTA can enhance structural performance, whereas excessive replacement (50%) may reduce stiffness and load resistance.

Conclusions

The Ceramic industries dump the waste products in nearby pit or vacant spaces, near their unit although notified areas have been marked for dumping. This leads to serious environmental and dust pollution and occupation of a vast area of land, and so it is very important to find a solution for this. So as to find a solution for this and to find out an economical construction material I choose this as my thesis topic. Literature review, procurement and testing of materials, mix design and casting of control specimen and specimens with replacement of 10%,25% and 50% of coarse aggregate with ceramic tiles has been done. The addition of 10% calcium carbonate has also done. And twenty eight day strength of all the mixes were found out and suitable comparisons are made. The conclusion of the work is as follows:

- a) The replacement of coarse aggregate by 25% of ceramic tile and adding 10% calcium carbonate is optimum and gives the maximum strength and is slightly higher than the conventional concrete mix.

- b) When the coarse aggregate is replaced by ceramic tiles at first the strength results seem to increase and after reaching an optimum it tends to decrease the strength.
- c) The addition of calcium carbonate will increase the strength of the concrete.
- d) The use of ceramic tiles in concrete will help in reducing the unit weight of concrete.
- e) Finite Element Analysis (FEA) using ANSYS Workbench 2023 R1 and SOLID185 elements effectively simulated beam behavior and validated the experimental results.
- f) All concrete mixes displayed near-linear load-deformation behavior within the elastic range, confirming predictable structural performance.

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